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Abstract

Background

Automated detection of return of spontaneous circulation (ROSC) is still an unsolved problem during cardiac arrest. Current guidelines recommend the use of capnography, but most automatic methods are based on the analysis of the ECG and thoracic impedance (TI) signals. This study analysed the added value of EtCO₂ for discriminating pulsed (PR) and pulseless (PEA) rhythms and its potential to detect ROSC.

Materials and methods

A total of 426 out-of-hospital cardiac arrest cases, 117 with ROSC and 309 without ROSC, were analysed. First, EtCO₂ values were compared for ROSC and no ROSC cases. Second, 5098 artefact free 3-s long segments were automatically extracted and labelled as PR (3639) or PEA (1459) using the instant of ROSC annotated by the clinician on scene as gold standard. Machine learning classifiers were designed using features obtained from the ECG, TI and the EtCO₂ value. Third, the cases were retrospectively analysed using the classifier to discriminate cases with and without ROSC.

Results

EtCO₂ values increased significantly from 41 mmHg 3-min before ROSC to 57 mmHg 1-min after ROSC, and EtCO₂ was significantly larger for PR than for PEA, 46 mmHg/20 mmHg ($p < 0.05$). Adding EtCO₂ to the machine learning models increased their area under the curve (AUC) by over 2 percentage points. The combination of ECG, TI and EtCO₂ had an AUC for the detection of pulse of 0.92. Finally, the retrospective analysis showed a sensitivity and specificity of 96.6% and 94.5% for the detection of ROSC and no-ROSC cases, respectively.

Conclusion

Adding EtCO₂ improves the performance of automatic algorithms for pulse detection based on ECG and TI. These algorithms can be used to identify pulse on site, and to retrospectively identify cases with ROSC.

Keywords: Return of spontaneous circulation (ROSC), ROSC detection, Capnography, End-tidal CO₂ (EtCO₂), Electrocardiogram (ECG), Thoracic impedance

Capnography: A support tool for the Detection of Return of Spontaneous Circulation in Out-of-Hospital Cardiac Arrest

Andoni Elola^{*,a}, Elisabete Aramendi^a, Unai Irusta^a, Erik Alonso^a, Yuanzheng Lu^b, Mary P. Chang^c, Pamela Owens^c, Ahamed H. Idris^c

Affiliation and addresses:

^a Communications Engineering Department.
University of the Basque Country UPV/EHU.
48013 Bilbao, Spain

^b Emergency and Disaster Medicine Center.
The Seventh Affiliated Hospital, Sun Yat-sen University.
Shenzhen, China

^c Department of Emergency Medicine.
University of Texas SouthWestern Medical Center (UTSW).
Dallas, United States

Corresponding author:

* Andoni Elola
email: andoni.elola@ehu.es
Tel. : +34946013956
Fax. : +34946014259

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Results: EtCO₂ values increased significantly from 41 mmHg 3-min before ROSC to 57 mmHg 1-min after ROSC, and EtCO₂ was significantly larger for PR than for PEA, 46 mmHg/20 mmHg ($p < 0.05$). Adding EtCO₂ to the machine learning models increased their area under the curve (AUC) by over 2 percentage points. The combination of ECG, TI and EtCO₂ had an AUC for the detection of pulse of 0.92. Finally, the retrospective analysis showed a sensitivity and specificity of 96.6% and 94.5% for the detection of ROSC and no-ROSC cases, respectively.

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Keywords

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1 **1. Introduction**

2 The main goal of resuscitative efforts during out-of-hospital cardiac arrest (OHCA) is to achieve
3 return of spontaneous circulation (ROSC). Those efforts include high quality cardiopulmonary
4 resuscitation (CPR), during which chest compressions should be minimally interrupted for actions
5 like rhythm analysis or pulse checks. Current pulse detection methods such as carotid pulse check,
6 or checking for signs of life as recommended by the current guidelines, are both time consuming and
7 inaccurate [1–5]. There is therefore a need for accurate and automated pulse detection methods [6]
8 that can be used by emergency medical personnel as a decision support tool to identify ROSC. Such
9 methods would contribute to improve therapy, reduce and shorten pauses in chest compressions,
10 and increase survival rates [7, 8].

11 Current guidelines support the use of capnography for early detection of ROSC [9]. Higher
12 values of end tidal CO₂ (EtCO₂), and sudden increases in EtCO₂ have been linked to ROSC in
13 OHCA [10–13]. Although some medical algorithms exist for the detection of ROSC using EtCO₂
14 values [14], the only automatic method based on capnography was recently proposed [15].

15 Most automatic methods for the detection of pulse in OHCA rest on the analysis of the ECG and
16 the thoracic impedance (TI). The TI signal shows low amplitude fluctuations for every effective
17 heartbeat [16], so features characterizing the TI signal have been proposed alone [17–19], or in
18 combination with ECG features [20–22] for the detection of pulse. In this context, detection of
19 pulse is framed as a classification problem with two types of organized rhythms: pulse-generating
20 rhythms (PR) and pulseless electrical activity (PEA).

21 The purpose of this study was to evaluate the added value of capnography for the classification
22 of PR/PEA during OHCA. First, EtCO₂ values were automatically detected in order to compare
23 the values between patients with and without ROSC, and to analyse how EtCO₂ changed as
24 the patient approached ROSC. Then, the added value of EtCO₂ for PR/PEA classification was
25 evaluated by developing machine learning PR/PEA classifiers.

26 **2. Materials**

27 For this study we analysed 1561 OHCA episodes retrospectively, treated by the Dallas
28 FortWorth Center for Resuscitation Research (UTSW, Dallas) using the Philips HeartStart MRx
29 device between 2012 and 2016. The device files included the ECG and TI recorded through

30 the defibrillation pads with sampling frequencies of 250 Hz/200 Hz respectively, and capnography
31 recorded through sidestream acquisition with a sampling frequency of 125 Hz. The electronic files
32 were linked to clinical annotations and ROSC was defined as palpable pulse in any vessel for any
33 length of time. The first ROSC instant annotated by the rescuer on scene was the gold standard;
34 based on that instant PR and PEA annotations were made automatically and patients with ROSC
35 and without ROSC were classified.

36 The following patient inclusion/exclusion criteria were applied. Only episodes with TI, ECG
37 and capnography were considered (n=835). Cases where ROSC was suspected but not annotated
38 by clinicians on site were excluded, which comprised patients transported to hospital (n=252), or
39 episodes with long periods (> 2 min) without compressions presenting an organized rhythm with
40 EtCO₂ above 25 mmHg (n=26). Episodes with suspected intermittent ROSC were also excluded,
41 these were episodes in which shocks or chest compressions (> 2 min) were delivered after the
42 annotated onset of ROSC (n=76). For our analysis of the ROSC cases, the capnogram had to
43 be available at least 4 minutes before and 1 minute after the onset of ROSC. If not, the case
44 was excluded (n=55). The final dataset contained 426 episodes, 117 with ROSC and 309 without
45 ROSC.

46 Figure 1 shows a 3-minute interval from two cases of the study dataset. In the ROSC case (top
47 panel) EtCO₂ increases at ROSC onset, and after ROSC the heart rate increases and there is pulse
48 related activity in the TI. In the no-ROSC case (bottom panel) EtCO₂ is always below 20 mmHg,
49 and although the heart rate changes during PEA there is no pulse related activity in the TI.

50 **3. Methods**

51 Three analyses were conducted: EtCO₂ levels in episodes with and without ROSC, development
52 and evaluation of a PR/PEA classifier using ECG/TI segments and EtCO₂ values, and a case study
53 of the use of the classifier to retrospectively identify cases as ROSC/no-ROSC.

54 *3.1. Analysis of EtCO₂ levels*

55 Onset and offset of each ventilation were automatically delineated in the capnogram using
56 a method introduced in a previous study [23]. For each ventilation, EtCO₂ was automatically
57 calculated as the maximum CO₂ value during the alveolar plateau (see Figure 1).

58 In ROSC cases, median EtCO₂ levels were computed every minute (MEtCO₂) in a five minute
59 interval around ROSC (4-min before to 1-min after). Similarly, for patients without ROSC, the
60 MEtCO₂ values were computed for each one of the last five minutes of the episode. The MEtCO₂
61 value for the last minute of the episode corresponds to the last minute before the EOE, i.e. the
62 instant when the monitor/defibrillator was disconnected.

63 *3.2. PR/PEA machine learning classifier*

64 Following the classical scheme proposed in previous studies [20–22], the detection of ROSC
65 implies the discrimination between PR and PEA once an organized rhythm is identified by the
66 shock advice algorithm. It is therefore a two class classification problem, for which, first, the dataset
67 of PR/PEA segments was defined, and then a classifier was designed using features extracted from
68 the ECG, TI and capnography signals.

69 *3.2.1. PR/PEA segment dataset*

70 PR and PEA segments of 3.2-s duration were extracted during intervals with no chest
71 compression artefacts. Pauses in chest compressions were automatically detected using the
72 compression depth signal from the CPR assist pad when available [24], or the TI otherwise [25].
73 Segments with large ECG amplitude oscillations (> 3.5 mV) were discarded as noisy, and then
74 organized rhythms (PEA or PR) were detected during the pauses using an offline version of a
75 rhythm analysis algorithm of a commercial automated external defibrillator (AED) [26]. In ROSC
76 cases, all segments before ROSC onset were labelled as PEA, and those after ROSC onset as PR
77 (see Figure 1, panel a). In no-ROSC cases, all segments were labelled as PEA (see Figure 1, panel
78 b). A minimum separation between consecutive segments of 20-s was enforced to foster ECG and
79 TI waveform diversity in the segments.

80 *3.2.2. Machine learning PR/PEA classifier*

81 Nine PR/PEA classification features were computed from the most recently proposed
82 algorithms, six ECG features introduced in [27], and three TI features [17, 22, 28]. These ECG
83 and TI features are described in detail in Appendix A. The MEtCO₂, the median EtCO₂ in the
84 minute before the analysis window (pause in chest compressions with organized ECG rhythm) was
85 also added. The features were combined in a Random Forest (RF) classifier, a machine learning
86 algorithm based on the aggregate vote of several independently designed uncorrelated decision trees

87 [29]. RF classifiers have shown excellent performance in many classification problems, including
88 PR/PEA classification [27], and are robust against annotation errors.

89 All patients were weighted equally to train the RF classifier and 300 trees were used. For
90 each segment, the RF classifier computes the probability of being PR (p_{pr}), and segments were
91 classified as PR for $p_{\text{pr}} > 0.5$ and as PEA otherwise. The classifier was trained and tested using
92 a patient wise 10-fold cross-validation procedure [30]. For each of the 10 folds, the algorithm was
93 optimized using 90% of the cases, and the accuracy results were obtained from the remaining 10%
94 (test fold). This procedure guaranteed that the optimization of the classifier and the estimation
95 of its accuracy were done on data from separate patients, and that the performance was assessed
96 using all available data.

97 *3.3. Case study: Retrospective identification of patients with ROSC*

98 Using the PR/PEA classifier, a simple method was developed to automatically identify patients
99 with ROSC in a retrospective analysis of a set of OHCA episodes. This method may be used as
100 an automated tool for post arrest debriefing or annotation. Complete episodes (until EOE) were
101 processed and the case was labelled as ROSC if from any three consecutive segments at least two
102 were identified as PR by the classifier.

103 Our ground truth was the ROSC instant annotated by clinicians on scene, which discriminated
104 the group of patients with ROSC and patients without ROSC, and the detection of episodes with
105 ROSC was evaluated using the test sets in the 10-fold cross validation procedure.

106 *3.4. Statistical analysis*

107 MEtCO₂ distributions did not pass the Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test, and are reported
108 as median and interquartile range (IQR). MEtCO₂ distributions at different times (within
109 ROSC cases) or between ROSC/no-ROSC cases were compared using the Mann-Whitney U test.
110 Differences were considered significant for $p < 0.05$.

111 PR/PEA classification was evaluated using Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curves,
112 and the area under the curve (AUC) was used as measure of performance [31]. The Youden index
113 was used to define the optimal point in the ROC curve, which gives equal importance to the
114 sensitivity (SE, for PR segments) and specificity (SP, for PEA segments) [32].

115 When the classifier was used as a retrospective tool to identify ROSC, SE and SP were defined
116 as the proportion of correctly identified ROSC and no-ROSC cases, respectively.

117 4. Results

118 The mean (standard deviation) durations were 58 (23) min and 38 (11) min for the episodes with
119 and without ROSC, respectively. The commercial AED algorithm detected 5098 segments with
120 organized rhythms. A total of 3639 PR segments were extracted from episodes with ROSC, and
121 1459 PEA segments, 308 from episodes with ROSC and 1151 from episodes without ROSC. Some
122 examples of the extracted ECG segments can be found in Figure 1 and Figure 4. The median
123 (IQR) ventilation rate per episode was 7.8 (5.7-10.5) min^{-1} .

124 The MEtCO_2 for ROSC cases were statistically significantly larger than for no-ROSC cases at
125 all time-stamps (Figure 2). Elevated EtCO_2 levels were observed in patients with ROSC, with an
126 upward trend from 41 mmHg (at 3 min before ROSC) to 57 mmHg close to ROSC onset (see Figure
127 2 a).

128 Figure 3 shows the ROC curves of the RF classifier for different features sets. The curves in
129 panel (a) were calculated using the whole dataset, while the curves in panel (b) were calculated
130 excluding the PEA segments extracted from patients with ROSC, that is the pre-ROSC PEA
131 segments. The analysis of the ROC curves is shown in Table 1. The ROC curves showed that the
132 AUC of the PR/PEA classifier increased as features from different sources were added. Including
133 MEtCO_2 in the classifier increased the AUC for all feature combinations, thanks to the added
134 uncorrelated information. Adding MEtCO_2 to an ECG-only and to an ECG+TI based classifiers
135 increased their AUCs in 3 and 2-points, respectively. The best classifier combined all features
136 and presented an AUC of 0.92 with a SE and SP of 84% and 86%, respectively (see Table 1).
137 MEtCO_2 alone was also a good classifier (AUC around 0.76), the median MEtCO_2 values were 46
138 (32-64) mmHg for PR and 20 (8-38) mmHg for PEA segments ($p < 0.05$).

139 The accuracy of the classifiers increased when PEAs that transitioned to PR (episodes with
140 ROSC) were not included. The accuracy increase was on average 4-points for all classifiers (see
141 Table 1). Significant differences were observed between PEAs in ROSC and no-ROSC cases.
142 The MEtCO_2 values of the PEA in the ROSC and no-ROSC cases were 31 (20-44) mmHg and 16
143 (7-35) mmHg ($p < 0.05$), respectively. The probabilities of being PR, p_{pr} , for the classifier with all
144 features were also significantly different for these two subgroups of PEA, 0.09 (0.03-0.29) for the
145 PEA from no-ROSC cases and 0.33 (0.11-0.58) for those of the ROSC cases ($p < 0.05$).

146 Figure 4 shows the performance of the PR/PEA classifier with three consecutive segments in

147 three patients. Each panel represents the 3 consecutive 3.2-second ECG and TI segments used
148 for analysis, and the capnogram in the 1-minute interval before the segment, which was used to
149 compute MEtCO_2 (depicted as a dashed line). The text on top of each segment shows the true
150 class followed by the class predicted by the classifier. The first example (panel a) shows a patient
151 achieving ROSC transitioning from PEA to PR in which all segments were correctly classified. The
152 first segment was taken 80 seconds prior to ROSC (PEA) and the other two after ROSC. It can
153 be observed that heart rate, TI activity and MEtCO_2 (specially in PEA/PR transition) increase
154 among consecutive segments. The second example (panel b) shows three correctly classified PEA
155 segments in a patient without ROSC. Despite having a heart rate above 60 bpm, low EtCO_2 values
156 and low circulation-related TI activity yielded the correct classification of the three segments and
157 of the patient without ROSC. The third example, however, corresponds to a patient without ROSC
158 incorrectly identified as patient with ROSC. Two of the segments were classified as PR because
159 the ECG was regular with a heart rate above 60 bpm, the TI showed large fluctuations and EtCO_2
160 levels were above 30 mmHg.

161 When the PR/PEA classifier with all features was used as a retrospective tool to automatically
162 identify episodes with and without ROSC, the SE and SP were 96.6% and 94.5%, respectively. Only
163 4 cases with ROSC were misidentified as no-ROSC, and 17 cases with no-ROSC were identified as
164 ROSC cases.

165 5. Discussion

166 Detection of ROSC remains a challenge in OHCA, and there is still a need for a reliable
167 monitoring of the hemodynamic state of the patient [6]. This study shows that EtCO_2 has great
168 potential to support the rescuer in the identification of ROSC, both as a stand-alone marker but
169 also in combination with the ECG and TI. This is, to the best of our knowledge, the first study
170 that demonstrates that the addition of EtCO_2 improves PR/PEA classification based on the ECG
171 or on the combination of ECG and TI.

172 The results shown in Figure 2 and Table 1 reveal that a three-signal classifier provides better
173 performance than two-signal solutions, which are better than a classifier based on a single signal.
174 These results may help in the design of PR/PEA classification systems, and different solutions
175 may be implemented depending on the availability or usability of the signals in a particular

176 monitor/defibrillator.

177 For this study, we extracted PEA segments from patients with and without ROSC, and we
178 relied on the ROSC onset annotations made by clinicians on site. We believe that is the most
179 realistic (and challenging) scenario, although we observed differences in the characteristics of the
180 PEA obtained from patients that ultimately recovered ROSC and those who did not. MEtCO_2
181 levels during PEA were significantly higher in patients that recovered ROSC, and the AUCs of
182 the PR/PEA classifiers increased by over 4-points when PEAs from patients that recovered ROSC
183 were not included. In fact, the SP for the PEAs of the patients that recovered ROSC was 61.2%,
184 significantly lower than 91.2% obtained for the patients with no ROSC. There are two main reasons
185 behind the differences in SP. First, the instant of ROSC annotated by clinician on scene and used
186 as gold standard might show some delay depending on the rescuer. Second, there are differences
187 between PEAs leading to PR (from ROSC patients) and PEAs not leading to PR (from patients
188 without ROSC). Rhythms from first group are more likely to be pseudo-PEAs since they present
189 a better prognosis, and they show different ECG characteristics and EtCO_2 values [33–39]. This
190 type of border rhythm challenges the design of an accurate classifier. An experiment supporting
191 these conclusions is detailed in the supplementary file. The p_{pr} obtained from the classifier was
192 significantly lower for PEA in no-ROSC cases, and as shown in Figure 5, the median value of p_{pr}
193 increases for PEA in ROSC patients as the patient approaches ROSC onset. This indicates that
194 the p_{pr} obtained from the RF classifier may serve as a potential surrogate hemodynamic marker
195 that could measure the evolution of PEA in response to therapy.

196 The analysis of the MEtCO_2 values for the intervals around ROSC (Figure 2 a) showed that
197 EtCO_2 values increase as the patient approaches ROSC, and the rise is higher closer to ROSC
198 onset, in line with previous findings [12, 13]. We also observed that EtCO_2 levels were maintained
199 after ROSC, or even decreased if ventilation rates were high. Abrupt increases in EtCO_2 can be
200 used to identify ROSC onset, but are of little use in a PR/PEA classifier due to its short period
201 utility time. During both PR and PEA, EtCO_2 may increase or decrease around high (PR) or low
202 (PEA) baseline levels. However, interrupting chest compressions only after a sudden increase in
203 EtCO_2 to check for an organized rhythm facilitate early detection of ROSC and minimize hands-off
204 intervals by avoiding unnecessary chest compressions pauses to check for pulse [9, 14]. The EtCO_2
205 levels reported in this study were high, which may be caused by the inclusion criteria applied to

206 the data that contained those patients with sustained ROSC.

207 The overall performance of the PR/PEA discriminator is high ($AUC > 0.9$), but slightly below
208 the scores reported by other methods based exclusively on the ECG [27] or combination of ECG
209 and TI [21, 22]. Those studies used segments selected ad-hoc for the processing of the ECG or
210 the TI, which might have introduced a positive bias in the results. Our dataset was automatically
211 selected, including all segments classified as organized rhythm by a commercial AED algorithm,
212 and segment labelling was based exclusively on ROSC annotations made by clinicians on site. In
213 fact, when we applied the method proposed in [27] to the dataset of this study, the SE/SP were
214 78.8%/84.1%, well below the 88.4%/89.7% reported in the original paper. This dataset reflects a
215 more realistic and difficult scenario for PR/PEA classification.

216 As an example of applicability of the PR/PEA classifier, a simple automatic tool to
217 retrospectively identify cases with ROSC was proposed. In our 426 cases, a simple method was
218 over 95% accurate, yielding a 96.6% SE and a 94.5% SP for the retrospective detection of ROSC.
219 These values are well above the 73.9% SE and 58.4% SP reported for an automatic algorithm based
220 on capnography trends alone [15].

221 Finally, the accuracy of the PR/PEA classifier supports its applicability as an automatic
222 decision support tool to aid clinicians in the identification of ROSC. The algorithm uses only
223 a 3.2-s analysis interval without chest compressions, so it can be used during CPR with minimal
224 interruptions to chest compressions. Furthermore, we used an automatic CO_2 based ventilation
225 detector that identifies the offset/onset of ventilations. This allows us to measure the $EtCO_2$ level
226 as the maximum value during the alveolar plateau in the capnography, which avoids some of the
227 problems associated with $EtCO_2$ readings (capnometry) at the end of the expiratory phase when
228 chest compression artefacts are present in the CO_2 waveform [40]. Each ventilation was delineated
229 using the algorithm proposed in [23], a software-based algorithm that could be integrated in any
230 equipment without hardware modifications. The algorithm is launched once the AED algorithm
231 has detected an organized rhythm, and it only requires waveform characteristics of the 3.2-s long
232 ECG and TI signals and the median of the $EtCO_2$ values in the minute prior to the analysis.

233 **6. Limitations**

234 This study shows three limitations. Firstly, the data were collected with the capnography
235 module of the Philips HeartStart MRx monitor/defibrillator. Using another capnometer might
236 alter the levels of EtCO₂. Secondly, our ground truth for all the experiments was the time of
237 ROSC annotated by the clinician on scene. Using an independent gold standard for circulation,
238 such as invasive blood pressure, would result in more robust conclusions. Lastly, there were no data
239 available on the advanced airway technique used on each patient. However, the reported EtCO₂
240 values might be affected by the used airway management technique (supraglottic/endotracheal).

241 **7. Conclusions**

242 The results of this study demonstrate the added value of the capnogram for the automatic
243 detection of ROSC in OHCA. The EtCO₂ level added discriminative power to the PR/PEA
244 classifier based on the ECG and the TI. The accuracy of the models increased significantly when
245 MEtCO₂ levels were added. This study shows that an automatic algorithm that uses capnography
246 can be implemented to reliably detect ROSC.

247 **Conflict of interest**

248 Dr. Idris receives research grants from the US National Institutes of Health (NIH) and serves
249 as an unpaid volunteer on the American Heart Association National Emergency Cardiovascular
250 Care Committee and the HeartSine, Inc. Clinical Advisory Board.

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256 **Appendix A. Signal processing and feature extraction**

257 Nine features (v_1-v_9) were computed from the ECG ($s[n]$) and the TI ($z[n]$) signals. The ECG
 258 was filtered between 0.5 Hz and 30 Hz using zero-phase filtering to remove baseline component and
 259 high frequency noise. The TI was resampled to 250 Hz and filtered between 0.7 and 7 Hz to remove
 260 fluctuations caused by ventilations and enhance the circulation component.

261 Six different features, v_1-v_6 , were calculated from the ECG as recently proposed in [27]:

- 262 • The first difference of the signal ($s_\Delta = s[n] - s[n - 1]$) was computed and the mean of its
 263 absolute value was the first feature:

$$v_1 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N |s_\Delta[n]| \quad (\text{A.1})$$

264 where N is the length of the segment in samples.

- 265 • The standard deviation of $s_\Delta[n]$:

$$v_2 = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{n=0}^{N-2} (s_\Delta[n] - v_1)^2}{N - 3}} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

- 266 • The kurtosis (tailedness) of the square and averaged (with a 125 ms moving average filter) of
 267 s_Δ was v_3 .

- 268 • Amplitude Spectrum Area (AMSA) is the sum of spectral amplitudes weighted by their
 269 frequency components. The spectral amplitudes at f_i , A_i , were calculated using the $N_F =$
 270 4096 point FFT of the Tuckey windowed $s[n]$ segment:

$$v_4 = \sum_i A_i \cdot f_i, \quad 2 < f_i < 30 \quad (\text{A.3})$$

- 271 • The energy of $s[n]$ at frequencies higher than 17.5 Hz:

$$v_5 = \frac{f_s}{2N_F} \sum_i A_i^2, \quad 17.5 < f_i < 30 \quad (\text{A.4})$$

- 272 • Fuzzy Entropy of $s[n]$, a measure of its regularity, was the v_6 feature.

273 PEA is defined as absence of palpable pulse when organized electrical activity of the heart is
 274 present. The TI signal shows small fluctuations for every effective heartbeat. Many efforts have
 275 been made to extract the circulation component of the signal using adaptive filters or ensemble
 276 averaging [20, 21, 41], but all of them need accurate QRS detection. Ruiz et al. and Alonso
 277 et al. considered the circulation component as a quasi-periodic signal and estimated its Fourier
 278 coefficients using least mean squares or recursive least squares algorithms. The instantaneous
 279 heart rate was computed from the QRS complexes. Risdal et al. applied ensemble averaging to
 280 the TI signal around QRS instants to extract the circulation component. However, in this study
 281 we considered only features independent of QRS complex detection, in particular those proposed
 282 in [17, 22, 28]:

- 283 • The mean power of the two half segments of $z[n]$ were computed and the minimum value
 284 assigned to v_7 [22].
- 285 • The power spectrum of the first difference of $z[n]$ was computed, and v_8 was its peak amplitude
 286 in the 1.5-4.5 Hz range [17].
- 287 • The normalized cross-correlation function was computed as follows:

$$r_{sz}(l) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{r_{ss}r_{zz}}} \sum_{n=1}^N s[n]z[n-l], \quad l = 0, \pm 1, \dots, \pm N - 1 \quad (\text{A.5})$$

288 where $r_{ss} = \sum_{n=1}^N (s[n])^2$ and $r_{zz} = \sum_{n=1}^N (z[n])^2$. The maximum peak of $r_{sz}[l]$ was v_9 [28].

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381 Figure Legends

- 382 Figure 1 ECG, Thoracic Impedance (TI) and capnography signals for a patient
383 with ROSC, panel (a), and without ROSC, panel (b). ROSC onset,
384 as annotated by a clinician on site, is represented by a red line in
385 the first example. The extracted 3.2-s segments are shaded in grey
386 and the ECG and TI (green) are zoomed in. Chest compression
387 intervals are depicted above TI signal. In the ROSC case a PEA
388 and a PR segments were extracted in the depicted interval, and two
389 PEA segments in the no-ROSC case. Ventilations were automatically
390 detected in the CO₂ curve, and the automatically measured EtCO₂
391 value is highlighted with red dots. In the ROSC case after pulse
392 recovery the ECG presents stable and normal QRS complexes and
393 heart rate, and chest compressions are stopped so there is no activity
394 in the impedance.
- 395 Figure 2 Median EtCO₂ (MEtCO₂) values and their interquartile ranges for
396 cases with ROSC (left) and no-ROSC (right). For ROSC cases the
397 interval around ROSC onset is analysed, in the no-ROSC cases the
398 5 min before the end of episode (EOE) are shown. MEtCO₂ was
399 calculated as the median EtCO₂ value of all ventilations in a 1-minute
400 interval before the indicated time-stamp.
- 401 Figure 3 ROC curves of the RF classifier for different feature sets. Panel (a)
402 shows results for the whole dataset, while panel (b) shows the curves
403 after excluding the PEAs from episodes with ROSC. The AUC value
404 for each classifier is shown between parentheses.
- 405 Figure 4 Examples of the case study. Panels (a), (b) and (c) show a
406 correctly identified patient with ROSC, a correctly identified patient
407 without ROSC, and a patient without ROSC incorrectly identified,
408 respectively. Each panel depicts the three consecutive PEA/PR
409 segments analysed. The text on top of each segment indicates its true
410 label followed by the predicted label by the classifier. The capnogram
411 corresponds to the minute before the onset of the segment and the
412 dashed horizontal line represents the MEtCO₂.
- 413 Figure 5 Time evolution of p_{pr} for the PEA segments as the patients approach
414 ROSC. Blue dots indicate values for each segment, and the red curve
415 is fitted to the median values of p_{pr} every 2 minutes.

(a) A case of a patient with ROSC

(b) A case of a patient without ROSC

Figure 1: ECG, Thoracic Impedance (TI) and capnography signals for a patient with ROSC, panel (a), and without ROSC, panel (b). ROSC onset, as annotated by a clinician on site, is represented by a red line in the first example. The extracted 3.2-s segments are shaded in grey and the ECG and TI (green) are zoomed in. Chest compression intervals are depicted above TI signal. In the ROSC case a PEA and a PR segments were extracted in the depicted interval, and two PEA segments in the no-ROSC case. Ventilations were automatically detected in the CO₂ curve, and the automatically measured EtCO₂ value is highlighted with red dots. In the ROSC case after pulse recovery the ECG presents stable and normal QRS complexes and heart rate, and chest compressions are stopped so there is no activity in the impedance.

Figure 2: Median EtCO₂ (MEtCO₂) values and their interquartile ranges for cases with ROSC (left) and no-ROSC (right). For ROSC cases the interval around ROSC onset is analysed, in the no-ROSC cases the 5 min before the end of episode (EOE) are shown. MEtCO₂ was calculated as the median EtCO₂ value of all ventilations in a 1-minute interval before the indicated time-stamp.

Figure 3: ROC curves of the RF classifier for different feature sets. Panel (a) shows results for the whole dataset, while panel (b) shows the curves after excluding the PEAs from episodes with ROSC. The AUC value for each classifier is shown between parentheses.

Figure 4: Examples of the case study. Panels (a), (b) and (c) show a correctly identified patient with ROSC, a correctly identified patient without ROSC, and a patient without ROSC incorrectly identified, respectively. Each panel depicts the three consecutive PEA/PR segments analysed. The text on top of each segment indicates its true label followed by the predicted label by the classifier. The capnogram corresponds to the minute before the onset of the segment and the dashed horizontal line represents the MEtCO₂.

Figure 5: Time evolution of p_{pr} for the PEA segments as the patients approach ROSC. Blue dots indicate values for each segment, and the red curve is fitted to the median values of p_{pr} every 2 minutes.

416 **Table Legends**

417	Table 1	ROC curve analysis of the machine learning classifier when the whole
418		PR/PEA dataset is considered and when the PEAs from ROSC cases
419		were excluded. The SE and SP are given for the optimal point according
420		to the Youden index.

	All PR/PEA segments			Excluding PEAs from ROSC		
	AUC	SE	SP	AUC	SE	SP
EtCO ₂	0.76	72.3	67.8	0.79	83.7	64.6
ECG	0.88	84.2	78.2	0.93	81.7	90.8
ECG+TI	0.90	86.7	81.6	0.94	88.4	87.0
ECG+EtCO ₂	0.91	86.3	81.5	0.95	91.8	84.2
ECG+TI+EtCO ₂	0.92	83.9	86.0	0.96	87.8	91.3

Table 1: ROC curve analysis of the machine learning classifier when the whole PR/PEA dataset is considered and when the PEAs from ROSC cases were excluded. The SE and SP are given for the optimal point according to the Youden index.